

Effect of perturbations on orbital density using Eulerian orbit dynamics

Liam M. Healy **Blake T. Halpin** **Scott T. Kindl**

Dynamics and Control Systems Branch
Spacecraft Engineering Division
Naval Research Laboratory
Washington, DC

AAS 21-217
31st AAS/AIAA Space Flight Mechanics Meeting

February 1, 2021

Density 1 hour after fragmentation

Our previous work

- ▶ We have discovered a way to do *Eulerian orbit dynamics*, propagating the spatial number density from a point fragmentation given an initial velocity distribution at that point.
- ▶ Conferences early 2016 to present, Journal of the Astronautical Sciences (online January 2019, in print 2020).
- ▶ This produces plots such as those shown at the left.

Density 8 hours after fragmentation

Our previous work

- ▶ We have discovered a way to do *Eulerian orbit dynamics*, propagating the spatial number density from a point fragmentation given an initial velocity distribution at that point.
- ▶ Conferences early 2016 to present, Journal of the Astronautical Sciences (online January 2019, in print 2020).
- ▶ This produces plots such as those shown at the left.

Perturbations and the two-point boundary value problem

- ▶ The goal of the present work is to introduce perturbations into the calculation and understand their effects on the spatial density.
- ▶ In order to do this, we need to use a propagator for perturbed motion, and the ability to solve the perturbed two-point boundary value (“Lambert”) problem.

The complete Lambert problem

- ▶ Density computation is based on Housen's method, which involves solving the Lambert problem.
- ▶ More precisely, we need to solve the *complete* Lambert problem, the Lambert problem for all of the routes (or *Lambert modes*) between the initial point of fragmentation r_1 and the final point in space r_2 after the specified elapsed time.
- ▶ Each mode has a mathematical solution, but that is not necessarily a *physical* solution.
- ▶ Eliminate trajectories that collide with the earth (dashed lines at left).

The perturbed Lambert problem

- ▶ PDE solution techniques
 - ▶ With perturbations, solve the two-point boundary value problem, or “perturbed Lambert” problem.
 - ▶ There are multiple ways to solve this problem, e.g. shooting, multiple shooting.
 - ▶ How to do differential correction.
- ▶ All methods need an initial solution; we use Russell’s iterated versine Lambert solver (2019) for the two-body problem.
- ▶ Method of particular solutions
 - ▶ Woollands et al. “Multiple Revolution Solutions for the Perturbed Lambert Problem using the Method of Particular Solutions and Picard Iteration”, JAS 2017.
 - ▶ We did not implement Picard iteration (see next).
 - ▶ Method of particular solution, where Jacobian is calculated numerically.

- ▶ We investigated several numerical propagators, an ongoing process.
- ▶ Focus on software easily called by a C program.
- ▶ High accuracy is *not* needed, but quick computation is.
- ▶ TUDAT was found to be too cumbersome to use as a library.
- ▶ Turn our attention to simple, quasi-inertial integration: no coordinate system rotations or “true of epoch”.
- ▶ Model J_2 only initially.
- ▶ Montenbruck and Gill (2000) have such an integrator written in C++, uses the Shampine-Gordon variable step integration technique.

Anomalies in the particular solution solver and numerical integrator

- ▶ Any iterative method, e.g. Newton's method, has the potential for being unable to obtain a solution meeting a specified accuracy requirement.
- ▶ Possibly check for four things
 - ▶ Near-singularity of Jacobian for Newton solution.
 - ▶ Iteration limit exceeded (100).
 - ▶ Maximum tolerable r_2 error.
 - ▶ Non-convergence, if r_2 error exceeds each of that of the last three iterations.
- ▶ r_2 error is the magnitude of the difference between the requested r_2 and that computed by propagating the initial state.
- ▶ First never occurred, third was intentionally disabled.
- ▶ If the non-convergence check is disabled, all occurrences become iteration limit exceeded errors, so this is just a time-saver (can be more than 50% faster overall).
- ▶ Integrator convergence failure, adjust tolerances, but even so, numerous errors (most at later times).

- ▶ Fragmentation of a satellite in equatorial circular orbit at 900 km altitude.
- ▶ Relative velocity density distribution is isotropic normal with standard deviation of 250 m s^{-1} .
- ▶ Compute the density in the source orbit plane and plot on a grid every 24 km.
- ▶ Compare with two-body result of the same problem.
- ▶ Elapsed time every hour for 1 through 16 hours after fragmentation.

Density

+1h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Density

+2h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Density

+3h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Results for J_2 perturbation

Density

+4h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Density

+5h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Density

+6h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Results for J_2 perturbation

Density

+7h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Density

+8h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Results for J_2 perturbation

Density

+9h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Results for J_2 perturbation

Density

+10h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Results for J_2 perturbation

Density

+11h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Results for J_2 perturbation

Density

+12h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Results for J_2 perturbation

Density

+13h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Results for J_2 perturbation

Density

+14h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Results for J_2 perturbation

Density

+15h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Results for J_2 perturbation

Density

+16h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

+1h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Particular solution solver anomalies

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

+2h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

+3h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

+4h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

+5h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

+6h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

+7h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

+8h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

+9h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Particular solution solver anomalies

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

Particular solution solver anomalies

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

+11h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

+12h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

Particular solution solver anomalies

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

+15h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Particular solution solver anomalies

Anomalies in perturbed Lambert solution

+16h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Density

+4h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Density

+4h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Density

+8h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Density

+8h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Density

+12h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Density

+12h00m from fragmentation time

L. Healy

Compute the RMS difference between J_2 and two-body densities of all non-anomaly points, and the fraction of the RMS to the mean density

Time (h)	RMS (km^{-3})	Fraction
2	2.01352×10^{-10}	0.000687
4	2.1493×10^{-9}	0.003409
6	6.487×10^{-10}	0.001668
8	2.81203×10^{-10}	0.000882
10	4.93766×10^{-10}	0.001842
12	5.81783×10^{-10}	0.001839
14	2.99139×10^{-10}	0.001342
16	1.36664×10^{-10}	0.001002

No particular pattern, not clear why it is so large at four hours.

- ▶ Conference papers <https://zenodo.org/communities/eod>
- ▶ YouTube videos <https://tiny.cc/eodvideos>
- ▶ 2019 JAS paper, open access: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40295-018-00144-1>